

A Comprehensive Study of Custom Change Data Capture on a Large Scale RDBMS

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Abstract : Change Data Capture (CDC) is a pivotal feature in Relational Database Management Systems (RDBMS) that facilitates the identification, tracking, and extraction of modifications made to data within databases. This paper provides a thorough examination of the principles, benefits, and implementation strategies associated with CDC in the context of RDBMS. The paper begins by elucidating the fundamental concepts of CDC and its significance in various data management scenarios, such as data warehousing, data integration, and real-time analytics. It explores the motivations behind adopting CDC and outlines the challenges it addresses in maintaining data consistency, integrity, and auditability. A critical aspect of the paper involves a detailed discussion of the steps involved in enabling a Custom CDC within an RDBMS environment. This includes selecting tables for CDC, configuring CDC settings, and understanding the structure of CDC tables. Practical examples are provided to illustrate the implementation process, with a focus on a prominent RDBMS like SQL Server. Furthermore, the paper addresses considerations for handling different types of changes (inserts, updates, deletes) and managing the overhead associated with CDC processes. The impact of CDC on system performance is thoroughly examined, and the paper proposes strategies to mitigate potential overhead.

IndexTerms - Data Integration, SQL, RDBMS, CDC, Change Data Capture, Change Tracking, Databases, Rowversion

1. INTRODUCTION

In the dynamic landscape of data management, the ability to track and respond to changes within a relational database is paramount. Change Data Capture (CDC) [1] emerges as a pivotal mechanism, offering a nuanced solution to monitor, capture, and propagate modifications made to data. This paper delves into the intricacies of CDC within the realm of Relational Database Management Systems (RDBMS) [2], unraveling its core principles, applications, and implementation nuances. The surge in data-driven decision-making has heightened the demand for real-time and accurate information. CDC addresses this need by providing a systematic approach to capture alterations in the database, facilitating tasks such as data warehousing, synchronization, and auditing. As organizations grapple with the challenge of maintaining data consistency and integrity, CDC emerges as a crucial tool in their arsenal.

The primary objective of this paper is to equip practitioners, administrators, and developers with a comprehensive understanding of CDC in the context of RDBMS [1]. It navigates through the fundamental concepts of CDC, elucidating its role in different data management scenarios and unraveling the motivations behind its widespread adoption. By grounding the discussion in real-world applications, the paper aims to bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical implementation. The journey begins with an exploration of the foundational principles of CDC, establishing a clear understanding of its relevance in an ever-evolving data landscape. Subsequently, the paper guides readers through the intricacies of enabling CDC within an RDBMS environment. Practical examples, particularly focusing on a prominent system like SQL Server [8], are provided to demystify the configuration process. As the implementation unfolds, attention is devoted to critical considerations, such as handling different types of changes, managing system overhead, and incorporating CDC seamlessly into data integration workflows.

The paper emphasizes the importance of robust logging and auditing mechanisms to ensure the reliability and accuracy of CDC processes, addressing concerns related to data governance and compliance. By amalgamating theoretical insights with practical implementation guidelines, this paper seeks to empower database professionals with the knowledge necessary to harness the transformative capabilities of CDC. It serves as a comprehensive guide, shedding light on the complexities and nuances of CDC within RDBMS, thereby enabling stakeholders to leverage this technology for enhanced Data Management and Integration Solutions [4].

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT: OPTIMIZING CHANGE DATA CAPTURE IN A LARGE-SCALE RELATIONAL DATABASE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM (RDBMS)

Change Data Capture (CDC) is a critical mechanism to identify, record, and propagate alterations within the database. However, the scale and complexity of modern database systems pose challenges that demand a focused investigation. The problem at hand involves designing and implementing an optimized CDC solution for a large-scale RDBMS environment. Key challenges include:

- Scalability: The RDBMS manages a massive volume of data, with tables containing millions or billions of rows. The CDC solution must be scalable to handle this scale efficiently, minimizing the impact on performance.
- Real-time Updates: As businesses increasingly demand real-time analytics [3] and decision-making, the CDC solution must provide near real-time updates. This requires minimizing latency in capturing and applying changes.
- Handling Diverse Changes: The RDBMS experiences a variety of changes, including inserts, updates, and deletes. The CDC solution must accurately capture and represent each type of change while maintaining data integrity.
- Resource Efficiency: The CDC process should be resource-efficient to prevent undue strain on system resources. Considerations must be made for storage, processing power, and memory usage.
- Integration with Data Warehousing: For effective data integration and analytics, the CDC solution should seamlessly integrate with data warehousing solutions, allowing for easy extraction and transformation of changed data.
- Error Handling and Recovery: Robust error-handling mechanisms are crucial. The CDC system should be capable of identifying, logging, and recovering from errors to ensure the reliability of the captured changes.
- Security and Compliance: Given the sensitive nature of data, the CDC solution must adhere to security standards and compliance requirements. This includes role-based access control, encryption, and auditability.
- Customization and Extensibility: Different tables within the RDBMS may have unique requirements. The CDC solution should offer customization options and extensibility to adapt to specific use cases and evolving business needs.

The goal is to develop a comprehensive CDC solution that addresses these challenges, providing an efficient and reliable mechanism for tracking changes in a large-scale RDBMS. This solution should enhance data management, support real-time analytics, and contribute to the overall efficiency and agility of the organization's data infrastructure.

3. CUSTOM CHANGE DATA CAPTURE (CDC)

3.1 About

There are different Change Data Capture techniques available out there to help deal with the problem at hand, out of which we are going to focus mainly on the Custom Change Data Capture Tracking [5]. We are not referring to the inbuilt SQL Server-Oracle CDC here but customizing it to ensure no Database enabling and changing is required here. It is often used in scenarios where we need to capture and analyze changes made to data over time at scale. Different types of Custom Change Data Capture techniques are outlined below.

3.2 Datetime based CDC

Datetime-based CDC is a strategy for tracking changes in a relational database by leveraging a datetime column to identify records that have been modified since a specified timestamp. This approach is particularly useful when we want to capture changes made to the data over time and is often employed in scenarios where the system doesn't provide built-in CDC features [8] or when customizing the tracking mechanism is required. Key Components in the CDC here are :

- Datetime Incremental Column: Each table subject to CDC includes a datetime column (e.g., LastModified) that records the timestamp of the last modification. This column acts as an incremental column to capture delta records. It could involve introducing a Default Date column, that captures introduced/modified timestamp.
- Timestamp Comparison: Changes are identified by comparing the timestamp in the datetime column with a reference timestamp. Rows with timestamps later than the reference timestamp indicate modifications.
- Custom Logic: Application logic is implemented to update the datetime column whenever a change occurs. This could involve updating the column automatically on every modification.

Example Implementation (Using a SQL DB): Consider a hypothetical scenario where we have an "Employee" table, and we want to implement a custom datetime-based CDC for tracking changes:

```
CREATE TABLE Employee (
    EmployeeID INT PRIMARY KEY,
    FirstName VARCHAR(50),
    LastName VARCHAR(50),
    LastModified DATETIME
);

ALTER TABLE Employee
ADD CONSTRAINT DF_Employee_LastModified
DEFAULT GETDATE() FOR LastModified;
```

Figure 1. Datetime CDC Table creation

This custom datetime-based CDC mechanism allows us to query the "Employee" table to identify records modified after a specific timestamp, enabling us to track changes over time and then use the LastModified to keep track of changes arriving. Below is a query, which does that at the cost of keeping track of the Incremental Column LastModified within the change interval.

```

DECLARE @CurrentrunTimestamp DATETIME = '2024-01-18T00:00:00',
        @PreviousrunTimestamp DATETIME = <PreviouslyCapturedWaterMark>;

SELECT
    EmployeeID,
    FirstName,
    LastName,
    LastModified
FROM
    Employee
WHERE
    LastModified >= @PreviousrunTimestamp AND LastModified < @CurrentrunTimestamp;

```

Figure 2. Datetime CDC Query creation

For a large transactions oriented system, which would require continuous ETL processing [7], it is required to record the LastModified timestamp each time records are extracted out of the table to ensure we only bring in Delta/Modified records. It is also possible data in the designated table could be loading when the extract query is running, so the Extraction can be run in either committed mode or we consider to include greater than or equal to(>=) condition over the query to extract concurrent data. It comes with a cost of duplicates, that should be handled by the downstream system which consumes data. This is applicable to any RDBMS that supports timestamp columns; these are widely used in large scale ETL processing. Important consideration here is that, if there is a failure in Extraction, then capturing the last run watermark would need to be canceled.

3.3 Numeric based CDC

Numeric-based CDC involves tracking changes in a relational database by utilizing a numeric column to represent a version or sequence number associated with each record. This approach is particularly useful when we want to capture changes and updates to records based on a numerical identifier that increases with each modification. Key Components in the CDC here are :

- **Numeric Version Column:** Each table subject to CDC includes a numeric column (e.g., VersionNumber) that serves as a version identifier for each record.
- **Version Incrementing Logic:** Whenever a record is modified, the numeric column is incremented to reflect the change. This could involve updating the column automatically on every modification.
- **Version Comparison:** Changes are identified by comparing the version number with a reference version. Rows with version numbers greater than the reference version indicate modifications.
- **Custom Logic:** Application logic is implemented to manage the incrementing of the numeric version column and handle updates.

Example Implementation (Using SQL DB): Consider a hypothetical scenario where we have a "Product" table, and we want to implement a custom numeric-based CDC for tracking changes:

```

-- Create the Product table with a VersionNumber numeric column
CREATE TABLE Product (
    ProductID INT PRIMARY KEY,
    ProductName VARCHAR(100),
    Price DECIMAL(10, 2),
    VersionNumber INT IDENTITY(1, 1)
);

```

Figure 3. Numeric CDC Sample Table creation

This custom Numeric based CDC mechanism allows us to query the "Product" table to identify records modified after a specific VersionNumber[8], enabling us to track changes over time and then use the VersionNumber to keep track of changes arriving. Below is a query, which does that at the cost of keeping track of the Incremental Column LastModified. For a large transactions oriented system, which would require continuous ETL processing, it is required to record the VersionNumber each time records are extracted out of the table to ensure we only bring in Delta records. Numeric based CDC primarily acts as an append only extraction because if we are using IDENTITY on our column, it essentially increments each time we have new records and would not get updated each time we have updates, so preferable to use the Numeric based CDC for appending only type of tables. Important consideration here is that, if there is a failure in Extraction, then capturing the last run watermark would need to be canceled.

```

DECLARE @CurrentrunVersionNumber INT = 5,
        @PreviousrunVersionNumber INT = <PreviouslyCapturedWaterMark>;

SELECT
    ProductID,
    ProductName,
    Price,
    VersionNumber
FROM
    Product
WHERE
    VersionNumber > @PreviousrunVersionNumber AND VersionNumber < @CurrentrunVersionNumber;

```

Figure 4. Numeric CDC Sample Query

3.4 Unique Identifier based CDC

UniqueIdentifier based CDC involves tracking changes in a relational database using a dedicated rowversion/UniqueIdentifier column to represent a version identifier for each record. This approach is particularly useful when we want to capture changes and updates to records based on a system-generated version number that automatically increments with each modification. Key Components are :

- Rowversion/Uniqueidentifier Column: Each table subject to CDC includes a rowversion column (e.g., RowVersion) OR a unique identifier that serves as a version identifier for each record. This can also be SCN(System Change Number) [9] in Oracle. This can be a binary identifier in SQL.
- Automatic Incrementing: The rowversion column is automatically incremented by the system whenever a modification occurs to the associated record. This ensures a unique and increasing version for each change.
- Version Comparison: Changes are identified by comparing the rowversion with a reference rowversion. Rows with rowversion values greater than the reference rowversion indicate modifications.
- Custom Logic: Application logic is implemented to manage updates to other columns and handle additional business logic related to the change.

Example Implementation (Using SQL DB): Consider a hypothetical scenario where we have a "Customer" table, and we want to implement a custom rowversion-based CDC for tracking changes:

```
CREATE TABLE Customer (
  CustomerID INT PRIMARY KEY,
  FirstName VARCHAR(50),
  LastName VARCHAR(50),
  RowVersion ROWVERSION
);
```

Figure 5. Rowversion CDC Sample Table creation

This custom Rowversion based CDC mechanism allows us to query the "Customer" table to identify records modified after a specific Binary identifier, enabling us to track changes over time and then use the Rowversion column to keep track of changes arriving. Below is a query, which does that at the cost of keeping track of the Incremental Column Rowversion.

```
DECLARE @ReferenceRowVersion ROWVERSION = 0x00000000000007D5;

-- Select CDC changes based on RowVersion column
SELECT
  CustomerID,
  FirstName,
  LastName,
  RowVersion
FROM
  Customer
WHERE
  RowVersion > @ReferenceRowVersion;
```

Figure 6. Rowversion CDC Sample Query

For a large transactions oriented system, which would require continuous ETL processing [7], it is required to record the Rowversion/UniqueIdentifier each time records are extracted out of the table to ensure we only bring in Delta records. UniqueIdentifier based CDC primarily acts as an upsert extraction because the identifier essentially increments each time we have new or updated records, making it more robust and reliable CDC to deal with concurrent or late arrival records. Basically, it acts like a combination of Datetime and Numeric because it serves both Appends and Updated records along with solving the problem of late arrival deltas. Important consideration here is that, if there is a failure in Extraction, then capturing the last run watermark would need to be canceled.

3.5 Hash based CDC

Hash-based CDC involves tracking changes in a relational database by using a hash function [3] to generate a checksum or hash value for each record. This approach is particularly useful when we want to detect changes based on the content of the data rather than relying on specific versioning columns. Key Components are:

- Hash Column: Each table subject to CDC includes a hash column (e.g., HashValue) that stores the hash value generated for the record's content.
- Hash Function: A hash function is applied to the record's relevant columns to generate a hash value. This hash value serves as a unique identifier for the content of the record.
- Checksum Comparison: Changes are identified by comparing the current hash value with a reference hash value. A difference in hash values indicates modifications.
- Custom Logic: Application logic is implemented to manage hash generation and updates to other columns based on the hash comparison.

Example Implementation (Using SQL Server): Consider a hypothetical scenario where we have an "Order" table, and we want to implement a custom hash-based CDC for tracking changes:

```

CREATE TABLE Order (
  OrderID INT PRIMARY KEY,
  ProductID INT,
  Quantity INT,
  OrderDate DATETIME,
  HashValue VARBINARY(64) -- Adjust the size based on hash
);

```

Figure 7. Hash CDC Sample Table creation

It is required to have a Hash Function to calculate hash based on the row values and it can be implemented as below :

```

CREATE FUNCTION dbo.GenerateHash(@ProductID INT, @Quantity INT, @OrderDate DATETIME)
RETURNS VARBINARY(64)
AS
BEGIN
  DECLARE @HashValue VARBINARY(64);

  -- hash generation logic here
  SET @HashValue = HASHBYTES('SHA2_256', CONVERT(VARCHAR, @ProductID) + CONVERT(VARCHAR, @Quantity) + CONVERT(VARCHAR, @OrderDate, 121));

  RETURN @HashValue;
END;

```

Figure 8. Hash CDC Sample Function

This custom Hash based CDC mechanism allows us to query the "Order" table to identify records modified after a specific calculated Hash, enabling us to track changes over time and then use the calculated Hash CDC column to keep track of changes arriving. Below is a query, which does that at the cost of keeping track of the Incremental Column HashValue :

```

UPDATE Order
SET
  ProductID = @NewProductID,
  Quantity = @NewQuantity,
  OrderDate = @NewOrderDate,
  HashValue = dbo.GenerateHash(@NewProductID, @NewQuantity, @NewOrderDate)
WHERE
  OrderID = @OrderID;

```

Figure 9. Hash CDC Sample Query

For a large transactions oriented system, which would require continuous ETL processing, it is required to record the calculated Hash [5] each time records are extracted out of the table to ensure we only bring in Delta records. Hash based CDC works as an upsert extraction mode because the identifier essentially increments each time we have new or updated records, but it comes with a cost of calculating Hash for each record while inserting into the DB, which is performance overhead. Important consideration here is that, if there is a failure in Extraction, then capturing the last run watermark would need to be canceled.

3.6 Full Snapshots

Full Snapshots CDC involves capturing the entire contents of a table, or a subset of columns, whenever changes occur. Unlike incremental CDC, which focuses on capturing only the changed data, full extract CDC retrieves all records, or a snapshot of selected columns, regardless of whether they have been modified. This approach is useful in scenarios where the goal is to extract the full state of the data for specific tables at specific points in time. Key Components are :

- Snapshot Columns: Define the columns to be included in the full extract. These can be all columns or a subset based on the usage of these columns in a distributed system.
- Timestamp or Versioning: Implement a mechanism to timestamp or version the extracted data, allowing us to identify when the extraction was performed.
- Custom Logic: Application logic is implemented to handle the extraction process, including selecting data and managing the timestamp or versioning.

Example Implementation (Using SQL Server): Consider a hypothetical scenario where we have a "ProductInventory" table to implement a custom full extract CDC to capture the entire state of the inventory at a specific point in time :

```

CREATE TABLE ProductInventory (
  ProductID INT PRIMARY KEY,
  Quantity INT,
  Location VARCHAR(50),
  LastModified DATETIME
);

```

Figure 10. Full Snapshots Sample Table creation

Full extract CDC mechanism allows us to query the "ProductInventory" table to extract all records at any point of time. When this query is executed, it captures the entire state of the "ProductInventory" table at the specified timestamp. Below is a sample query :

```

DECLARE @ExtractionTimestamp DATETIME = '2024-01-18T12:00:00';

-- Full extract query
SELECT
    ProductID,
    Quantity,
    Location,
    @ExtractionTimestamp AS ExtractionTimestamp
FROM
    ProductInventory;

```

Figure 11. Full Snapshots Sample Query

Custom full extract CDC is often used in data warehousing scenarios where periodic snapshots of data are needed for analysis or reporting purposes. It is less efficient than incremental CDC for tracking changes but serves specific use cases where historical snapshots are essential.

4. OBSERVATIONS

The choice of a Change Data Capture (CDC) strategy depends on the specific requirements, use cases, and characteristics of the chosen large-scale Relational Database Management System (RDBMS) [9]. Each CDC approach has its advantages and trade-offs, and the best choice often depends on factors such as data volume, performance considerations, and the nature of changes.

When performed a detailed usage of all these patterns for broader & large RDBMS at scale operations, some findings unfolded and here's the result of these findings based on previously discussed CDC strategies:

- UniqueIdentifier-based CDC:
 - Pros:
 - Automatic versioning without explicit management.
 - Provides a system-generated version number for each record.
 - Cons:
 - Limited to capturing changes at the record level.
 - UniqueIdentifier is captured at DB level, since rowversion is a DB counter and when used at a very large scale, performance needs to be monitored
 - May not be suitable for tracking changes in specific columns.
- Datetime-based CDC:
 - Pros:
 - Straightforward implementation with a timestamp.
 - Granular control over capturing changes at specific points in time.
 - Cons:
 - Requires careful management of timestamp precision.
 - May not capture changes in between timestamp updates.
- Numeric-based CDC:
 - Pros:
 - Offers a custom version identifier for each record.
 - Can be suitable for scenarios where a numeric version is meaningful.
 - Cons:
 - Requires explicit management of the version number.
 - May not be as robust for capturing changes across multiple columns.

Figure 12. CDC with Full Snapshots approach

- Hash-based CDC:
 - Pros:
 - Identifies changes based on content, useful for scenarios where specific column changes matter.
 - Provides the flexibility of muting no-ops because of the way hash can be constructed.
 - Provides a checksum for record integrity.
 - Cons:
 - May not efficiently handle large-scale changes.
 - Requires careful consideration of hash function efficiency.
- Full Extract CDC:
 - Pros:
 - Captures the entire state of selected columns at specific points in time.
 - Suitable for data warehousing scenarios requiring periodic snapshots.
 - Cons:
 - Inefficient for large-scale databases with frequent changes.
 - May result in a high volume of extracted data.

4.1 Conclusion and Summary of the Research

For scenarios where capturing changes efficiently and incrementally is critical, rowversion-based or datetime-based CDC would be suitable. If a meaningful version number is important for tracking changes, numeric-based CDC can be considered. Hash-based CDC [5] can be beneficial when changes in column content need to be precisely tracked. Full Extract CDC is appropriate for periodic snapshots in data warehousing scenarios but may not be efficient for continuous change tracking. Ultimately, the best CDC strategy for a large-scale RDBMS depends on the specific use case, performance considerations, and the nature of changes within the chosen system. It's recommended to carefully evaluate the requirements and test the chosen strategy in a representative environment to ensure optimal performance.

4.2 Discussion Points

The exploration of Custom Change Data Capture (CDC) within Relational Database Management Systems (RDBMS) reveals a diverse landscape of strategies, each tailored to address specific needs and nuances within the realm of data tracking and modification. In concluding this paper, several key takeaways emerge:

- Tailored Solutions for Varied Needs: The variety of custom CDC mechanisms discussed, including date time-based, numeric-based, rowversion based, hash-based, and full extract, underscores the importance of tailoring solutions to the specific requirements of the data and the use case. It is also worth considering use cases when Custom CDC [3] may not fit the need when a change capture is required for each unique instance and when it leads to multiple overrides. This means when there is a need to check how often a table is modified, how critical each change is and how often the dependent system needs to react. Change logs can be done as a custom CDC as well and these types of unique occurrences can still be detected by having a monitoring system, which consistently detects and actionizes when a particular scenario/pattern occurs.
- Granularity and Precision: The choice of CDC strategy depends on the desired granularity of change tracking. Rowversion-based and datetime-based mechanisms excel at capturing changes at the record level, while numeric-based and hash-based approaches offer precision in tracking changes within specific columns.
- Efficiency vs. Completeness: Trade-offs exist between efficiency and completeness. Incremental mechanisms like rowversion-based or datetime-based CDC are efficient for continuous tracking, while full extract CDC provides completeness at the cost of higher resource utilization.

- Considerations for Large-Scale Environments: In large-scale RDBMS environments, considerations such as scalability, performance, and resource efficiency become paramount. Careful evaluation and testing are essential to ensure that the chosen custom CDC strategy aligns with the scale and dynamics of the database.
- Extensive control on changes: When a large-scale RDBMS has massive updates, tracking them through in-built transaction logs becomes complex because of overhead built across the system. This is when Custom CDC gives the flexibility of controlling the changes extracted while still being able to fully retain ACID properties. Native features like in-built CDC would escalate performance challenges.
- Adaptability and Evolution: The dynamic nature of data and business requirements necessitates an adaptable approach. Custom CDC solutions should be designed with flexibility in mind, allowing for adjustments and optimizations as the database environment evolves.
- Integration with Data Warehousing: Custom CDC plays a crucial role in data warehousing scenarios where periodic snapshots or comprehensive data extracts are required. The choice of CDC strategy should align with the data warehousing needs, balancing data completeness with processing efficiency.

In conclusion, Custom Change Data Capture in RDBMS empowers database administrators [4] and developers to tailor their change tracking mechanisms to the unique demands of their systems. While each strategy brings its own set of considerations, the overarching goal is to strike a balance between precision, efficiency, and adaptability. As technology and data requirements evolve, the custom CDC landscape will continue to be a dynamic field, driving innovations in data management and integration solutions within the ever-expanding realm of relational databases. It's crucial to carefully evaluate the trade-offs, test the chosen strategy in a representative environment, and ensure that it meets the performance and business requirements of the system. Additionally, ongoing monitoring and adjustments may be necessary to adapt the CDC strategy to changing needs and data characteristics.

4.3 Algorithms

One of the Custom Data Capture techniques presented in this document primarily utilized SQL in-built hash function to get hash bytes, which runs mainly based on SHA2-256(Secure Hashing Algorithm) hashing algorithm. It can be customized to also use the MD5(Message Digest) algorithm [3]. The Unique Identifier CDC makes use of rowversion, which is varbinary construction of the SQL in-built per DB counter. It is a 8 byte binary and can vary per each RDBMS.

5. CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The author declares no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

REFERENCES

- [1] Fikri Muhaffizh Imani; Yohana Dewi Lulu Widyasari; Satria Perdana Arifin, Optimizing Extract, Transform, and Load Process Using Change Data Capture, 2023 6th International Seminars IEEE Xplore
- [2] Dhamotharan Seenivasan, Muthukumaran Vaithianathan, Real-Time Adaptation: Change Data Capture in Modern Computer Architecture, ESP International Journal of Advancements in Computational Technology 2022
- [3] J Shan, M Goldwasser, U Malik, B Johnston, Book of SQL for Data Analytics 2022
- [4] Madhavi Vaidya, Book of RBMS In-Depth 2021
- [5] Harry Chandra, Analysis of Change Data Capture Method in Heterogeneous Data Sources to Support RTDW, 2018 4th International Conference IEEE Xplore
- [6] Denny; I. Putu Medagia Atmaja; Ari Saptawijaya; Siti Aminah, Implementation of change data capture in ETL process for data warehouse using HDFS and apache spark, 2017 International Workshop on Big Data Systems
- [7] Ross Mistry, Shirmattie Seenarine, Book of Microsoft SQL Server 2012 Management and Administration
- [8] Muhammad Younus Javed; Asim Nawaz, Data Load Distribution by Semi Real Time Data Warehouse, 2010 Second International Conference IEEE Xplore
- [9] Darshan M. Tank, Amit Ganatra, Y.P. Kosta, C.K. Bhensdadia, Speeding ETL Processing in Data Warehouses Using High-Performance Joins for Changed Data Capture (CDC), IEEE International Conference 2010